

GEOPOLYMER VERSUS CEMENT-BASED TEXTILE-REINFORCED MORTAR: DIAGONAL COMPRESSION TESTS ON MASONRY WALLS REPRESENTATIVE OF INFILLS IN RC FRAMES

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ABSTRACT

The in-plane retrofitting of masonry structures with textile reinforced cement-based mortars (TRM) has been one of the most effective strengthening methods developed in the past decade. The paper investigates experimentally the potential of metakaolin-based geopolymers as a matrix for commercial basalt and glass textile reinforcing grids. Standard in-plane tests were carried out on single-leaf masonry wall specimens strengthened with ordinary cement-based and new geopolymer-based TRM thus offering a performance assessment of the two matrices. The test results showed that geopolymer-based TRM can reach performance levels surpassing the standard cement-based retrofitting system in terms of the cracking and peak shear strength as well as the deformation capacity.

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KEYWORDS

TRM; masonry infill; structural retrofitting; geopolymer; metakaolin; basalt textiles; glass textiles; diagonal strength; shear strength; shear strain.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.